

Identification of Subsurface Cavities by Geoelectric Method

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ABSTRACT:

Research has been conducted on the identification of subsurface cavities using geoelectric methods. Subsurface cavity is a natural phenomenon that commonly occurs in areas that have limestone rocks. The existence of underground cavities can result in the occurrence of ablesan in the form of sinkholes. Sinkholes have occurred in several places with varying sizes. Sinkhole as a result of underground cavity, this cavity is very dangerous to the building above it. For this reason, cavity identification needs to be done before starting construction. In this study, cavity identification was carried out using geoelectric methods. The research took three different locations, two where voids were already visible and one as a case study. The result is that the geoelectric method can detect voids very clearly. The gelistrik method is highly recommended as one of the methods to detect voids in the subsurface.

Keywords: identification, cavity, subsurface, geoelectric method.

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Problem

Subsurface cavities are a common natural phenomenon in areas that have limestone rocks [1]. The existence of underground cavities can lead to sinkhole [2]. Several locations have occurred sinkholes due to underground cavities such as the incident in China found in early May 2017. Precisely in the Guangxi Zhuang autonomous region, near Ping'e village in Leye county. This giant hole 193 metres deep has a base length of 306 metres and a width of 150 metres. In Indonesia there are also sinkholes that originate from underground cavities such as the case in the Gunung Kidul area, Central Java which occurred in 2020. Even in Bali it has also happened, such as what happened recently, namely a sinkhole on the Tegallalang District tourist route near Tampaksiring, Gianyar, Bali, Wednesday (13 September 2023). The sinkhole is about 50 metres deep and 30 metres wide.

The width and depth of sinkholes can vary from a few metres to hundreds of metres and from less than 1 metre to more than 100 metres deep. The shape of the sinkholes can be bowl or saucer shaped, while others are tubular with vertical walls. There are also some that collect water and form natural pools.

Here are some of the sinkhole locations that have occurred in Indonesia.

- a. Surabaya, East Java, in 2018. It occurred around Siloam Hospital or near BNI Gubeng towards Jalan Sumatera.
- b. Maros, South Sulawesi, in 2019. Occurred in Lebbotengae Village, Cenrana District.
- c. Sukabumi, West Java, in 2019. Occurred in a paddy field near a residential area. West Bandung, West Java, in 2022. It is not known when the sinkhole occurred in that place.
- d. Gunung Kidul, Yogyakarta
- e. Tegallalang, Gianyar, Bali, on Wednesday (13/9/2023). The hole with a diameter of about 30 metres and a depth of 70 metres cut off access to the Tegallalang-Tampaksiring tourist road in Gianyar.

Basically, there are two most common types of sinkholes, namely collapse and subsidence [3]. Sinkholes occur when there are cavities in the bedrock below the karst surface. These cavities form when slightly acidic rainwater absorbs carbon dioxide as it flows through the soil, making it more acidic. The dripping rainwater then flows freely through the cracks in the bedrock, slowly expanding into tunnels and cavities. Over time, if the cave space becomes large enough, the roof can no longer support the weight above it and can collapse, opening a large hole [4].

Considering the case of sinkholes as a result of underground cavities, it is necessary to identify the existence of underground cavities in advance when building on them, especially in areas with the potential for underground cavities. Identifying the presence of subsurface cavities is very important to know the position and depth of the cavity, so as to prevent accidents [5]. Cavities in the subsurface cannot be seen directly, for this reason a method is needed, namely a method that can map subsurface conditions. One of them is the geoelectric method.

The geoelectric method is one of the methods that can be used in mapping subsurface conditions [6]. This method works by injecting a high voltage low frequency alternating electric current into the earth (soil) [7]. As a result of current injection, a potential difference will arise in the earth. By measuring the amount of current strength injected (I) and the potential difference caused (V), then based on Ohm's law the amount of resistivity can be measured, namely [8]:

$$\rho_a = K \Delta V / I$$

With ρ_a is apparent resistivity (Ωm), V is the potential difference and I is the current strength, K is a geometry factor that depends on the configuration of the geoelectric method used. If using the Wenner configuration then:

$$K = 2 \pi a$$

With K is the geometry factor, π is a constant (3.14) and a is the distance between electrodes.

The scheme of the geoelectric method can be seen in the following

Figure 1. Schematic of the Geoelectric Method

By using the geoelectric method, the subsurface resistivity value will be obtained [9]. However, the resistivity value (ρ_a) is an apparent resistivity. To obtain the real resistivity, the data needs to be processed with the Res2divn programme [10]. The amount of resistivity of various materials can be seen in Table 1 below [11]. The magnitude of this resistivity value is still strongly influenced by its environment, for example sand which in the table is worth 1-1000 $\Omega.m$ if it is completely dry can have a resistivity of 1000 $\Omega.m$, but for sand with water it can be worth 100 $\Omega.m$. Likewise with other materials. In the table it appears that air has an infinite (very large) resistivity. Thus it can be interpreted that if geoelectric measurements in the dominant limestone area are found to have a large resistivity value, then the area can be interpreted as a cavity. This cavity has the potential to form a sinkhole [12].

Table 1. Rock Resistivity Value

Material	Resistivity (Ωm)
Air	~
Pyrite	0.01-100
Quartz	500-800000
Calcite	1×10^{12} - 1×10^{13}
Rock salt	30 - 1×10^{13}
Granite	200 - 10000
Andesite)	1.7×10^2 - 45×10^4
Basalt (wet)	1000 - 4×10^4
Basalt (dry)	10 - 1.3×10^7
Limestone	500-10000
Sandstone	200-8000
Shales	20-2000
Sand	1-1000
Clay	1-100
Ground water	0.5-300
Sea water	0.2
Magnetite	0.01-1000
Dry gravel	600-10000
Alluvium	10-800

Research Objectives

The purpose of this research is to demonstrate that geoelectric methods can be used to detect voids in the subsurface by providing examples at several locations and providing one example for a case study.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Site

The research was conducted in the Jimbaran area and on Lembongan Island Bali where both areas are limestone.

Equipment Used

The equipment used for data collection is a resistivity meter set consisting of a main set, namely the Naniura Geoelectric Model NRD 300 HF, cables, electrodes, batteries, handy talky, GPS, hammers, books, and laptops and the Res2Divn program.

Data Collection Method

The method used in data collection is the Wenner configuration geoelectric method. This method uses four electrodes installed sequentially with the same distance between electrodes. Two electrodes on the edge are used as current injection electrodes, while two electrodes in the middle are used as potential measuring electrodes. Measurements were taken along the measurement trajectory. The data obtained are the current value (I) and potential difference (V).

Data Analysis Method

The current strength data (I) and potential data (V) that have been obtained are analysed with the Res2Dinv program so that the real resistivity value is obtained. To make it easier to visualise the situation in the field, the real resistivity data is then drawn into the resistivity contour. It is this contour that is interpreted. If a very large value is obtained, it means that the area is a cavity area.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Geological Conditions of the Research Area

There are three locations where data was collected, two locations in the Jimbaran area and one location on Lembongan Island. The geology of the three research areas is limestone [13].

Figure 2. Geological map of the research area

Measurement and interpretation data

Measurement and interpretation data of the first location

Data at the first location was taken at Jimbaran Green Hill located in South Kuta District, Badung Regency, Bali Province. The location coordinates are approximately $8^{\circ}47'01.4''$ LS; $115^{\circ}09'08.1''$ BT (8.783726 LS; 115.1516888 BT) at an altitude of 186 m above sea level (Figure 3). The rocks in this area are dominated by limestone. On the western cliff wall, there is a cave. Three passes were made above the cave (cavity), namely L1, L2 and L3. The measurement results are as follows:

Figure 3. The First Research Location (L1,2,3: measurement trajectory)

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/place/Jimbaran+Greenhill/@-8.7837524,115.1527457,186m/data=!3m1!1e3!4m5!3m4!1s0x2dd244f0887e2e61:0xeccecffdc56ec0da18m2!3d-8.7868882!4d115.1563935>

Figure 4 (a,b,c). Resistivity Contours of the First Location Measurement Trajectory

The rock conditions above the cave can be explained based on geoelectric data as follows.

Figure 5 (a,b,c). Interpretation of the First Location Resistivity Contours

In general, the three measurement results can be interpreted as follows:

- a. It appears that the cave (cavity) part is detected with a very large resistivity characteristic, the resistivity value is above 15,000 Ω .m, while the limestone value is between 500-10,000 Ω .m.
- b. The variation in resistivity above the cave indicates that the limestone above the cave has begun to weather. The rock at the top is more weathered than the rock at the bottom, as shown in Figure 4.
- c. The presence of small fractures in the ceiling of the cave as shown in Figure 7 in the geoelectric data is indicated by the resistivity variation between 200 - 2000 Ω .m.

Figure 6. The Rock at the Top is More Weathered than the Rock at the Bottom

Figure 7. Small Fractures in the Cave Ceiling

Research in the first location can be concluded that sinkholes can occur in limestone areas [1] and can be detected by geoelectric methods [6] based on resistivity contrast [11].

Measurement data and interpretation of the second location

The research at the second location was conducted on Nusa Lembongan Island with the coordinates of the measurement location around the geographical position at 8.6881789 LS and 115.428934 BT, at an altitude of 10 m above sea level (Figure 7). Two passes were made as shown in Figure 8.

The surface of the research area appears to be weathered limestone as shown in Figure 10. On the shoreline there is also a cavity (Figure 11).

Figure 8. Secon Research Location

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/place/Nusa+Lembongan/@-8.6881789,115.428934,180m/data=!3m1!1e3!4m5!3m4!1s0x2dd26d9f537b69f3:0xdc1b94bd6c67a033!8m2!3d-8.6785828!4d115.4555858!5m1!1e1>

Figure 9. Measurement Trajectory of the Second Location (L1; L2 = Measurement trajectory)

Source: (<https://earth.google.com/web/@-8.68798671,115.42898665,7.01957868a,174.85408097d,35y,0h,0t,0r>)

Figure 10. Photo of Weathered Rock at the Second Location

Source: Personal document

Figure 11. Photo of the Cave on the Shoreline

The measurement results on each track at the second location after being analysed with the Res2dinv program produce cross-sectional contours of the real resistivity track. Interpretation refers to resistivity data, and local and regional geological data of the study area. The measurement results and their interpretation can be described as follows.

Figure 12. Resistivity Cross Section Contour of Trajectory 1

Trajectory 1 Figure 2. The first layer, up to a depth of 1.99 m (2 m), shows a resistivity of 100 Ω .m - 300 Ω .m which indicates that there is limestone that has been weathered, not hard. The presence of a large resistivity near the surface around the 60 m position indicates that there are cracks in the limestone piles as building materials that are buried below the surface until they are visible at the surface.

The second layer, at position 11.25-21.75 m, depth 2.58-4.36 m; there is a large resistivity between 1000-1500 Ω .m indicating a cavity as a continuation of the cave seen on the shoreline (Figure 10). At position 50.25-59.25 m, depth 3.16-4.36 m, there is a large resistivity between 1000-1500 Ω .m also indicating the presence of a cavity. The resistivity value in the cavity has dropped because the surface of the cavity has been exposed to seawater. These two cavities are not connected because they are bounded by more compact (massive) rocks with resistivity between 400-900 Ω .m. At position 23.25-48.75 m depth 2.58-4.36 m there is a resistivity between 400-900 Ω .m which indicates the presence of more compact (massive) limestone than limestone that has been weathered on the surface.

The third layer, starting from a depth of 4.97 to a depth of 10.04 m there are rocks with a resistivity of 400-900 Ω .m which indicates the presence of rock.

Lintasan 2:

Figure 13. Resistivity Cross Section of Trajectory 2

Trajectory 2 Figure 13. The first layer, the presence of a large resistivity at the position of 24.75-32.25 m with a resistivity of 1542-8514 $\Omega.m$ on the surface indicates the presence of impact limestone building materials, as observed in the field. At position 45.75 m, depth 0.28-0.85 m, there is a large resistivity with a value of 4749.70-1157.30 $\Omega.m$ as a result of the presence of concrete castings (visible concrete when installing geoelectric electrodes). The presence of small resistivity (<100 $\Omega.m$) in the first layer indicates the influence of water, presumably due to watering from the villa next door. In general, it also appears that the first layer has resistivity values between 100-300 $\Omega.m$, up to a depth of 2.58 m, indicating that the limestone in the surface area has been weathered as seen on the surface (Figure 9).

The second layer, in the middle at 18.75-27.75 m with a depth of 3.76-6.82 m, has a large resistivity (1015-1227 $\Omega.m$) indicating a cavity as a continuation of the cave seen on the shoreline (Figure 10). Based on observation, part of the cavity wall is wetted by seawater. That is why the periphery of the cavity has a smaller resistivity. However, the cavity is surrounded by more compact (massive) limestone with a resistivity of 400-900 $\Omega.m$.

In general, Site 2 can be interpreted as follows:

- In general, the existing rocks are limestone.
- On the surface, up to a depth of 2.58 m, there appears to be limestone rocks that have been weathered.
- In the middle section between 2.58-6.82 m there appears to be a cavity. This cavity can be seen all the way to the shoreline.
- At the bottom, below a depth of 7 m, there are limestone rocks that are more compact (massive) than the rocks on the surface.
- Research in the second location can be concluded that sinkholes can occur in limestone areas [1] and can be detected by geoelectric methods [6] based on resistivity contrast [11].

Measurement data and interpretation of the third location

The third site is located in Pecatu Village in South Kuta District, Badung Regency, Bali Province with coordinates 8.841675 LS 115.106366 East at an altitude of 132 m above sea level. The research location as shown in the picture:

Figure 14. The Third Research Location Source:

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/8%C2%B050'30.0%22S+115%C2%B006'22.9%22E/@-8.8426493,115.1071296,658m/data=!3m1!1e3!4m4!3m3!8m2!3d-8.8416634!4d115.1063464?entry=ttu>

Resistivity contour of the third location research track Trajectory

The measurement results at the third location can be interpreted as follows:

Figure 15. Resistivity Contours of the Third Location Research Track

The results of the analysis of the measurement results of the geoelectric method found that the rock resistivity in the area ranged from 461.19-3385.60 Ω .m, which indicates that the area up to a depth of 20 m consists of limestone with weathering conditions, water content, there is also a more compact limestone. There is no indication of a sink hole. The difference in resistivity indicates that the limestone in the area has different conditions, namely the level of weathering and water content of the rock.

The results of the analysis of the measurement results of the geoelectric method found that the rock resistivity in the area ranged from 443.39-1820.10 Ω .m, which indicates that the area up to a depth of 20 m consists of limestone with weathering, water content, and some more compact limestone. There is no indication of a sink hole. The difference in resistivity indicates that the limestone in the area has different conditions, namely the level of weathering and water content of the rock.

Based on the data of the two trajectories, it can be concluded that in the case study at the third location, the two trajectories do not indicate the presence of an empty space / cave hole (sink hole) because there is no visible resistivity contrast [11].

CONCLUSION

Based on the above discussion, it can be concluded that geoelectricity method can be used to identify cavities.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest in this research.

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